

Characterization of Biocompatible Gellan Gum Fractions for Prolonged Retention in Ocular Drug Delivery Systems

Gulnur S. Tatykhanova^{1,2,*}, Rysgul N. Tuleyeva^{2,3}, Nargiz N. Gizatullina^{1,2}, Daulet B. Kaldybekov^{2,3}, Yuliia V. Bardadym⁴, Vladimir O. Aseyev⁴, Sarkyt E. Kudaibergenov^{2*}

¹ Laboratory of engineering profile, Satbayev University, Almaty, Kazakhstan, e-mail: gulnur-ts81@yandex.kz

² Institute of Polymer Materials and Technology, Almaty, Kazakhstan, e-mail: skudai@mail.ru

³ Department of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Kazakhstan, e-mail: daulechem@gmail.com

⁴ Department of Chemistry, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland, e-mail: vladimir.aseyev@helsinki.fi

Abstract. Gellan gum (GG) emerges as a promising candidate for developing polymeric carriers with extended retention on the ocular surface, aiming to enhance the efficacy of topical ocular drug delivery systems. This study undertakes the purification of commercial GG through fractional dissolution and ultrasonic treatment, producing fractions characterized by ¹H, ¹³C NMR, FTIR spectroscopy, and thermogravimetric analysis. The intrinsic viscosity of GG samples was measured in a 0.025M tetramethylammonium chloride solution, and their molecular weights were calculated via the Mark-Kuhn-Houwink equation. Methodological choices regarding synthetic procedures, solvents, and reagents were guided by considerations of biocompatibility, aligning with the end goal of drug delivery applications. The study further explores the mucoadhesive potential of GG fractions with varying molecular weights for ocular drug delivery, utilizing an *in vitro* flow-through technique with fluorescent detection on freshly excised bovine corneal mucosa surfaces. The findings under-score the viability of GG formulations in enhancing ocular drug retention and pave the way for future applications in topical ocular therapeutics.

Keywords: commercial low acyl gellan gum, fractional dissolution, ultrasound treatment, reduced viscosity, intrinsic viscosity, Mark-Kuhn-Houwink equation, viscosity average molecular weight

Introduction

In the realm of ocular health, the treatment of various eye conditions often hinges on the application of eye drops. However, a significant challenge arises as less than 5% of the applied dose typically reaches the intraocular tissues when administered via conventional eye drops. This is related to the rapid loss of the instilled solution (continuous production of tear fluid, blinking reflex, nasolacrimal drainage) and poor permeability of ocular membranes [1]. Addressing this concern becomes crucial, and one promising avenue lies in enhancing the lipophilic character of drugs to substantially improve ocular absorption. The quest for precision in drug delivery has become a focal point in modern medicine, prompting the pharmaceutical industry to prioritize the development and implementation of innovative drug delivery systems. Notably, approximately 25% of global drug sales now comprise medications equipped with enhanced delivery systems [2-4]. There were many methods and improvements in ocular drug delivery developed over the last decades exploring more effective treatments for different ocular diseases. Nevertheless, this field of medicine remains one of the most challenging.

In the pursuit of enhancing the efficacy of ocular drug delivery, extending the contact time between the drug and the eye's internal structures emerges as a pivotal strategy. The significance of prolonged contact lies not only in its simplicity but also in its potential to increase the bioavailability of ophthalmic drugs. This becomes particularly crucial when considering the convenience and benefits associated with a single daily intake for the patient [5].

Various approaches have been explored to achieve this goal, each presenting its own set of advantages and drawbacks. One notable strategy involves the utilization of water-soluble biopolymers, aiming to extend the contact time and potentially enhance the amount of drug penetration. On the other hand, viscous semi-solid preparations such as gels, ointments, and films have also been considered. While these preparations can offer prolonged contact, they may induce side effects such as stickiness, blurred vision, and reflex blinking **due to the thickness of the formulation**, thereby causing discomfort or irritation to the eye [6,7].

There are several approaches to prolong the duration of ocular drug residence time of ophthalmic formulations, including the use of in situ gelling systems. Following instillation, these systems exhibit a phase transition in response to variations in temperature (i.e., Pluronic F127), pH (e.g., carbomers and cellulose acetates), and ionic strength (e.g., alginate, etc.) [8-11]. Additionally, corneal and conjunctival surfaces are covered with a thin layer of mucus that hydrates and lubricates the ocular surfaces as well as protects them from pathogens [12]. Thus, mucoadhesive polymers are also commonly employed to enhance retention time.

The ocular bioavailability of eye drops could be substantially improved when water-soluble mucoadhesive polymers are used as a part of the formulation. Adhesiveness of these materials and their retention on mucosal tissues of the eye depend on several mechanisms of action as those favoring ionic interactions that promote strong hydrogen bonding with hydroxyl, carboxyl and amino groups; polymers with high molecular weight (generally >100kDa) [13]; chain flexibility (able to interpenetrate into the mucus and form chain entanglements); and the rheological properties of eye drops, etc. [14] The mucoadhesive properties of these polymers are mostly based on the mix of several mentioned mechanisms.

Exploring alternative methods, in situ gelation systems present a promising avenue where droplets, initially in liquid **form during storage**, but transform into a **viscoelastic gel** upon contact with the eye's surface, **thereby resulting in improved patient compliance and reduced administration frequency**. This approach aims to mitigate the discomfort associated with prolonged use of semi-solid preparations. Additionally, modern nanotechnology introduces a novel dimension to the field, offering nanocarriers as a means to increase both the contact time and penetration ability of ocular drugs [11, 15-17].

To address this, we propose the use of an aqueous solution of gellan gum, which undergoes a sol-gel transition in the presence of sodium, potassium, and calcium ions containing in lacrimal fluid. Following **administration** to the eye, the gellan gum is expected to form an ultrathin transparent film **on mucus membrane, therefore enhancing ocular retention and precorneal drug loss. This, in its turn, can lead to more efficient drug absorption.**

GG is a polysaccharide obtained by deacetylation of exocellular polysaccharide produced by *Pseudomonas elodea*. The main components of GG are α -L-rhamnose, β -D-glucuronic acid, and β -D-glucuronic acid residues, which form a repeating tetrasaccharide unit [18,19]. GG has the property of forming a gel, which can be induced by the presence of cations [20]. The gel is formed through the formation of double helical structures, which then aggregate into a three-dimensional network through complexation with cations and hydrogen bonding with water.

As we navigate through the diverse strategies designed to extend contact time and enhance the bioavailability of ophthalmic drugs, this article delves into the intricacies of these approaches, shedding light on their potential applications, benefits, and challenges in the realm of ocular drug delivery.

This article delves into the current landscape of ocular drug delivery, highlighting the role of GG in shaping the future of pharmaceutical advancements [21-23].

Materials and Methods

Materials

Gellan gum (GG) was purchased from Zhejiang DSM Zhongken Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (China) ($M_n = 10^6$ g/mol estimated by viscosity). Acetone ($\geq 99.8\%$) and isopropanol ($\geq 99.5\%$, Fischer-Chemicals Oy) were used in the purification of GG. Deuterium oxide (D_2O , 99% D, Euriso-Top) were used in NMR experiments. Dialysis membranes (molecular weight cut off 3.5 kDa and 12-14 kDa) were purchased from Spectrum Laboratories. Milli-Q water with a resistivity of 18.2 M Ω cm at 298 K was used for all experiments. Sodium bicarbonate, fluorescein isothiocyanate-labeled dextran (FITC-dextran), fluorescein sodium salt (NaFl) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Gillingham, UK). Calcium chloride dihydrate, sodium chloride were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Loughborough, UK). Deionized water was used throughout the experiments involving aqueous solutions.

Characterization

1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy

Solutions of GG and its fractions (10 mg/mL) were prepared in D_2O . 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of samples were recorded using a Bruker 500 MHz NMR spectrometer (Bruker, UK) at 60°C. Bruker's TopSpin™ 3.6.2 software was used for analysis of spectra.

FTIR spectroscopy

FTIR spectra of gellan gum and its fractions were registered on PerkinElmer Spectrum One FT-IR spectrometer (PerkinElmer, USA) using an iD5 attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory equipped with a diamond crystal. Samples were scanned from 4000 to 650 cm^{-1} . The spectra were plotted and analyzed using the OriginLab 2021 software.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis was performed using a LABSYS evo TGA instrument. Samples (3–5 mg) were heated from 25 to 800 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere. Thermograms were plotted and analyzed using the OriginLab 2021 software.

Elemental analysis

Elemental analysis was used to compare the composition of the pristine (commercial GG) and purified GG fractions. Elemental composition was determined using a HANAU Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH (Germany), using the vario MICRO cube with sulfanilamide as a standard. Three samples (~2 mg of dry polymer per measurement) were studied and the results were averaged.

Other stages of sample preparation

The ultrasonic processor UP400S (400 Watts, 24kHz) “Hielscher Ultrasound Technology” was used for sonicating the samples. Separation of insoluble Gellan fractions was performed by Sigma laboratory centrifuge 2K15C “B.Braun Biotech International”. The samples were freeze dried using a FreeZone plus 2.5 L “LABCONCO” freeze dryer. The viscosity of solutions was measured using the system PVS 1 “LAUDA”, Micro-KPG Ubbelohde auto, Nr. 1c, K=0.03.

***Ex vivo* retention studies on bovine corneal tissues**

Whole intact bovine eyeballs with eyelids were received from P.C. Turner Abattoirs (Farnborough, UK) immediately after slaughter of the animals, packed and transported to the laboratory in insulated plastic containers. These tissues were visually assessed in terms of any damage and corneal opacification present. The corneal tissues were carefully excised using disposable sharp blades, avoiding contact with their surfaces, and then used for evaluating the retention properties of the formulations using the methodology previously developed by the Khutoryanskiy research group [15, 23–25]. Each corneal tissue was pre-rinsed with 1 mL of

simulated tear fluid (STF), mounted on a microscope glass slide with the testing surface facing upward, placed in Petri dishes and then stored at 4 °C in a refrigerator. All tissues were used within 12 h of retrieval.

STF solution used to wash a mucosal surface was prepared as described in a previous report [26]. Briefly, sodium chloride (670 mg), sodium bicarbonate (200 mg), and calcium chloride dihydrate (8 mg) were dissolved in 100 mL of deionized water. The pH of the STF solution was adjusted to 7.40 due to the natural tear pH being around a neutral value and the solution was maintained at 37 °C throughout mucoadhesion experiments using a water bath.

Experiments were conducted with the corneal tissues maintained at 37 °C and 100% relative humidity in an incubator to mimic physiological conditions. Each cornea, already mounted on a glass slide, was placed on a substrate, fixed at an angle of 20° and prewarmed for 1 min within the incubator before starting each *ex vivo* mucoadhesion experiment. Next, prewarmed aliquots (200 µL) from 0.3% (w/v) gellan gum formulations prepared in deionized water containing 1 mg/mL fluorescein sodium salt (NaFl); two controls of NaFl (1 mg/mL) and FITC-dextran (0.3% w/v) solutions were applied onto the corneal surface and were then repeatedly irrigated with STF (pH 7.40) at a constant flow rate of 100 µL/min using a syringe pump for 30 min (total washing time). The flow rate selection was intentionally set higher than the physiological secretion rate of tear fluid (~1–2 µL/min in human eyes) for practical reasons [27]. This adjustment was made to expedite the experiments and ensure they could be conducted within a reasonable timeframe. The fluorescence images of corneas were acquired at predetermined time intervals after each washing cycle using a Leica MZ10F stereomicroscope (Leica Microsystems, UK) fitted with the GFP filter (blue, $\lambda_{\text{emission}} = 520$ nm) and Leica DFC3000G digital camera at 1.0× magnification, with 30 ms of exposure time and a 1.0× gain. These images were then analyzed using ImageJ software (version 1.54g, 2023, NIH, USA.) by measuring the pixel intensity after each washing with STF. The pixel intensity of the blank tissues (i.e. the background microscopy image of each corneal surface before administering a fluorescent test material) was subtracted from each measurement. Data were normalized and converted into % mucosal retention values.

All retention tests were performed in triplicate for each formulation, the mean \pm standard deviation values were calculated and then evaluated statistically.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis of data from mucoadhesion studies was performed using GraphPad Prism software (version 8.0; San Diego, CA, USA.). Data were compared and assessed for significance using two-tailed Student's *t*-test and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Bonferroni *post hoc test*, where $p \leq 0.05$ was considered as the statistically significant criterion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of Purified Commercial GG in Aqueous Solution

The purified GG, due to the presence of carboxylic groups in glucuronic acid fragments, displays polyelectrolyte behavior. As a result, the dependence of η_{sp}/C cannot be extrapolated to zero polymer concentration for determining the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ (Figure S1). Typically, this issue can be addressed in two ways: (1) using an empirical Fuoss equation, or (2) adding low-molecular-weight salt to suppress the polyelectrolyte effect.

As shown in Figure S2, the curve in Figure S1 was linearized using the Fuoss equation [28, 29]:

$$\frac{c}{\eta_{sp}} = \frac{1}{[\eta]} + k_{FS} \frac{1}{[\eta]} c^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

where η_{sp} – specific viscosity, which is determined as $(\eta - \eta_s)/\eta_s$, where η is the viscosity of the polymer solution and η_s is the viscosity of the solvent; $[\eta]$ – is the intrinsic viscosity, which is determined by extrapolation of η_{sp}/C to $C \rightarrow 0$; k_{FS} is the Fuoss coefficient; C - is the concentration of the polymer in the solution.

The intrinsic viscosity of GG, determined using the Fuoss equation, was found to be $5680 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$.

Fractionation and determination of the molecular weights of GG

The extremely high molecular weight of commercial low acyl GG in the range of $(0.5-1) \approx 10^6$ limits the widespread use of GG as an eye drops of a drug delivery system. A 1.0 % w/v GG solution is poorly soluble in water; it forms a fraction of soluble chains and a dispersed fraction of swollen gellan particles. To reduce the molecular weights and to improve the solubility in water, the fractionation of GG was carried out by two methods: fractional dissolution and ultrasonic treatment. Using the method of fractional dissolution, we obtained reduced molecular weights of GG (Figure 1). Here GG-1, GG-2, GG-3, GG-4 refer to gellan gum fractions isolated by the fractional dissolution method.

Figure 1. Concentration dependences of the reduced viscosities of GG fractions obtained by fractional dissolution

At first GG (1.0 % w/v) was dissolved for 24 hours in deionized water at 50°C . The turbid solution/dispersion was centrifuged for 30 min at 40°C with a rotation speed of 5000 rpm. The upper transparent fraction of the liquid was collected and precipitated in acetone (1:4 by volume). Then the separated precipitate was dissolved again in deionized water, and the process was repeated 4 times. The stages of cleaning commercial GG can be viewed in Figure S3. GG was separated from the water-acetone mixture by vacuum filtration using Whatman 541 filter paper and dried for 30 min. Then it was dissolved in deionized water and subjected to dialysis against deionized water (cut off 12–14 kDa) for at least 24 hours. The product was freeze-dried and collected in the form of dry fluffy white fibers. The intrinsic viscosities of GG fractions, found from the extrapolation of η_{sp}/C to $C \rightarrow 0$, are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Chains scissoring of commercial GG was carried out using ultrasound treatment to obtain GG fractions of lower molecular weights. 1.0 % w/v GG samples ultrasonically treated at 50°C during 5, 10, 30, 60, and 120 min were centrifuged at 50°C for 1 h. Every time the separated supernatant was precipitated in isopropanol, dialyzed, and freeze-dried. The intrinsic viscosities of ultrasonically treated GG samples were measured in an aqueous solution containing 0.025M

tetramethylammonium chloride (Figure 2). Here 1-GG, 2-GG, 3-GG, 4-GG, 5-GG are gellan gum fractions obtained by ultrasonic treatment during 5, 10, 30, 60, and 120 minutes.

Figure 2. Concentration dependences of the reduced viscosities of GG after 5-, 10-, 30-, 60- and 120-min treatment by ultrasonic source

The viscosity average molecular weights (M_η) of GG fractions calculated according to Mark-Kuhn-Houwink equation in 0.025M tetramethylammonium chloride $[\eta] = 7.48 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot M_w^{0.91}$ [30] are summarized in Tables 1 and Table 2. It is revealed that the ultrasonic treatment of GG leads to gradual decrease of both $[\eta]$ and M_η . It could be associated with cleavage of glycosidic linkages and degradation of GG [31]. In contrast, in fractional dissolution, the low molecular weight fractions are separated at the beginning, and at the end, fractions with high molecular weights remain.

Table 1. The intrinsic viscosities and M_η of GG fractions obtained by fractional dissolution

Fractions	Intrinsic viscosity, $\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$	$M_\eta \cdot 10^{-5}$, Dalton
GG-1	1430	6.43
GG-2	1592	7.23
GG-3	1792	8.23
GG-4	1949	9.03

Table 2. The intrinsic viscosities and M_η of GG fractions obtained by ultrasonic treatment

Fractions	Ultrasonic treatment, min	Intrinsic viscosity, $\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$	$M_\eta \cdot 10^{-5}$, Dalton
1-GG	5	1395	6.25
2-GG	10	1204	5.32
3-GG	30	1086	4.75
4-GG	60	939	4.04
5-GG	120	895	3.84

Spectroscopic characterization of commercial gellan and GG fractions

FTIR and NMR spectroscopy revealed no significant differences between the purified and pristine GG. Thus, there was no indication that GG was not completely deacetylated and the

fraction was removed during purification. This conclusion is also confirmed by elemental analysis, which shows the same carbon and hydrogen content in samples.

^1H , ^{13}C NMR and FTIR spectra GG fractions obtained by fractional dissolution and ultrasound treatment are shown in Figures 3-6. The results show no significant differences between the samples, confirming the absence of structural changes in the course of fractionation. The spectra of GG obtained at 60 °C showed the presence of four characteristic peaks corresponding to: -CH of rhamnose (δ 5.27 ppm), -CH of glucuronic acid (δ 5.11 ppm), -CH of glucose (δ 4.88 ppm), and -CH₃ of rhamnose (δ 1.86 ppm).

Figure 3. Repeating monomeric units of GG and ^1H NMR spectra of GG fractions obtained by fractional dissolution of commercial gellan

Figure 4. ^1H NMR spectra of GG fractions obtained by ultrasonic treatment of commercial gellan

The ^{13}C NMR spectra of commercial gellan and GG fractional dissolution are shown in Figure 5. Although the detailed signal assignment has not been made at the present stage, the carbonyl peak (δ 175.2 ppm) for glucuronic acid ring, methylol peaks (δ 61.2 and δ 61.7 ppm) for glucose rings, and the methyl peak (δ 17.6 ppm) for the rhamnose ring are clearly seen. Thus, ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy showed clear and well-distinguishable peaks, each of which can be correlated with specific functional groups in the polysaccharide composition.

Figure 5. ^{13}C NMR spectra of different fractions of GG obtained by fractional dissolution. a) GG-1, b) GG-4, c) commercial gellan

Figure 6 displays the FTIR spectra of GG, and its fractions obtained by fractional dissolution. Absorption peaks observed at 3370 cm^{-1} and 1408 cm^{-1} are associated with OH vibrational modes.

The peak at 2921 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-H stretching vibrations. The peaks at 1604 cm^{-1} and 1039 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of C=O and C-O bonds, respectively.

Figure 6. FTIR spectra of commercial and GG fractions

Thermograms of commercial and GG fractions are presented in Figure 7. It can be observed that the thermal properties of the GG samples are similar, but an increase in molecular weight slightly raises the decomposition temperature.

Figure 7. TGA curves of commercial gellan and GG fractions

Viscosity of GG fractions in model tear fluid

The reduced viscosities of GG fractions were measured in model tear fluid, which was adjusted by adding NaCl, KCl, and CaCl_2 according to Ref. [32] (Figure 8). The viscosity of GG

significantly increases upon addition of model tear fluid. The optimal concentration of model tear fluid that leads to effective viscosification of the GG fractions is approximately 0.16-0.17 mg/mL, as further increases in salt concentration result in the viscosity leveling off. Moreover, the viscosification of the aqueous solution of GG increases in the order: GG-4 >> GG-2 > GG-1 and is more pronounced in high molecular weight fractions. This approach may be important for retaining of drug, for instance ofloxacin loaded to gel matrix of gellan, as shown in our previous report [16].

Figure 8. The dependence of the reduced viscosity of 0.2 % w/v solutions of GG fractions on the concentration of model tear fluid at 25 °C. 1) GG-1, 2) GG-2, 3) GG-4.

Mucoadhesion studies, particularly retention on *ex vivo* bovine corneal tissues

The potential use of GG fractions (with different molecular weights) in ocular drug delivery formulations was examined by assessing mucoadhesion on freshly excised bovine corneal tissues using a well-established *in vitro* flow-through technique with fluorescent detection. These formulations were prepared with NaFl (1 mg/mL), which serves as a fluorescent marker that facilitates easy detection and measurement of mucosal retention levels. The method has been extensively used to evaluate the retention properties of various test materials on different mucosal surfaces, including ocular tissues [23,24,33–35]. The effectiveness of this technique was validated against other established methodologies used to assess mucoadhesive properties [36].

Patients respond better to *in situ* gelling systems, which are administered as solutions that instantly form gels upon contact with the ocular surface. Some studies have demonstrated the advantages of these systems, including reduced nasolacrimal drainage, sustained and prolonged drug release, and enhanced bioavailability resulting from an extended precorneal residence time [37,38].

Figure 9 displays the exemplar fluorescence microphotographs of the retention of fractionated gellan gum formulations, as well as solutions of NaFl (1 mg/mL) and 0.3% (w/v) FITC-dextran (both used as non-mucoadhesive controls) on *ex vivo* bovine cornea taken after washing with varying volumes of STF (pH 7.40; flow rate 100 μL/min) over 30 min. The fluorescent images were then analyzed with ImageJ software, and fluorescence intensity values were normalized and converted to 100% retention values (Figure 10). During mucoadhesion experiments conducted at 37°C and 100% relative humidity within the incubator, all GG formulations formed *in situ* gels and the percentage of their retention on the cornea was estimated.

After analyzing the images, it was revealed that all GG formulations exhibited similar retention abilities on freshly isolated bovine corneas, as values were not significantly different from each other ($p>0.05$). However, they exhibited superior retention ($p<0.001$) compared to solutions of NaFI (served as a negative non-mucoadhesive control) and FITC-dextran (served as a non-gel-forming polymer control). According to the findings, the increased mucoadhesive performance of the gellan gum formulations until the end of washing cycles is likely attributed to the fact that the samples form a thin layer of **viscous physical gels (ion activated in situ gel)** upon interaction with salt ions in the STF solution. Additionally, NaFI and FITC-dextran solutions showed significantly lower retention capability, with >90% of them being washed out from the corneal surface.

Figure 9. Selected exemplar fluorescence microphotographs showing mucosal retention of 0.3% (w/v) solutions of fractionated GG formulations (with different M_n) containing 1 mg/mL fluorescein sodium salt (NaFI); as well as free 1 mg/mL NaFI and 0.3% (w/v) FITC-dextran (both served as non-mucoadhesive controls), on freshly isolated bovine corneal tissues after washing with varying volumes of STF solution (pH 7.40; flow rate 100 μ L/min). Fluorescence microscope parameters: magnification – 1.00 \times ; exposure time – 30 ms; gain – 1.0 \times . Scale bars correspond to 2 mm.

Figure 10. Percentage mucosal retention of 0.3% (w/v) solutions of fractionated GG formulations (with different Mw) containing 1 mg/mL fluorescein sodium (NaFl); as well as fluorescein NaFl and 0.3% (w/v) FITC-dextran (both served as non-mucoadhesive controls) on ex vivo bovine corneas after washing with varying volumes of STF (pH 7.40; flow rate 100 μ L/min). The corneal retention was assessed using a wash-off in vitro assay over 30 min. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation values (n = 3). Statistically significant differences are represented as *** – $p < 0.001$; ** – $p < 0.01$; * – $p < 0.05$; ns – denotes no significance.

Conclusions

This study presents a comprehensive approach to the purification and characterization of gellan gum (GG) for potential use in drug delivery systems specifically designed for topical application in the eye. Utilizing two distinct fractionation techniques –fractional dissolution and ultrasonic processing – we successfully achieved the fractional separation of commercial gellan gum, isolating nine fractions with molecular weights ranging from $3.8 \cdot 10^5$ to $9.0 \cdot 10^5$ Daltons. The structural identity of these GG fractions was confirmed using a variety of analytical methods, including ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, FTIR spectroscopy, and thermogravimetric analysis. Furthermore, we investigated the impact of model tear fluid on the viscosity characteristics of gellan, finding that optimal thickening of an aqueous gellan solution occurs at a model tear fluid concentration of approximately $0.016\text{--}0.017 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Mucoadhesion experiments demonstrated that all tested GG formulations exhibit similar retention abilities on freshly isolated bovine corneas.

In conclusion, we have optimized a formulation for eye drops involving gellan based on the "sol-gel" transition mediated by tear fluid. This highlights a promising method for the development of effective ocular drug delivery systems, leveraging the unique properties of GG to enhance drug retention and bioavailability on the ocular surface.

References

1. Järvinen T, Järvinen K. Prodrugs for improved ocular drug delivery. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 1996; 19:203–224.

2. Hacker MC., Nawaz HA. Multi-functional macromers for hydrogel design in biomedical and regenerative medicine. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2015; 16:27677-27706.
3. Gan L, Gan Y, Zhu X, Zhu J. Novel microemulsion in situ electrolyte-triggered system for ophthalmic delivery of lipophilic cyclosporine A: In vitro and in vivo results. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics.* 2009; 365:143-149.
4. Venkatalakshmi R, Sudhakar Y, Madhu C, Varma M. Buccal Drug Delivery System Using Adhesive Polymeric Patches. *Int. J. Pharm Sci and Res.* 2012; 3(1):35-41.
5. A. Ludwig M. Van Ooteghem. Influence of viscolysers on the residence of ophthalmic solutions evaluated by slit lamp fluorophotometry. *S.T.P. Pharma Science.* 1992; 2:81-87.
6. Dudinski O, Finnin BC, Reed BL. Acceptability of thickened eye drops to human subjects. *Curr. Ther. Res.* 1983; 33:322-337.
7. Sintzel MB, Bernatchez SF, Tabatabay C, Gurny R. Biomaterials in ophthalmic drug delivery. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 1996; 42:358-374.
8. Khutoryanskiy VV. *Mucoadhesive materials and drug delivery systems, Mucoadhesive Materials and Drug Delivery Systems.* John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Chichester, UK. 2014.
9. Khutoryanskiy VV. Advances in mucoadhesion and mucoadhesive polymers. *Macromol. Biosci.* 2011; 11:748-764.
10. Fatemeh A, Mohammad E, Abbas HR, Abraham JD, Hossein H. Overview on Natural Hydrophilic Polysaccharide Polymers in Drug Delivery, *Polymers For Advanced Technologies.* 2018; 29:2564-2573
11. Al Khateb K, Ozhmukhametova EK, Mussin MN, Seilkhanov SK, Rakhypbekov TK, Lau WM, Khutoryanskiy VV. *In situ* gelling systems based on Pluronic F127/Pluronic F68 formulations for ocular drug delivery. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics.* 2016; 502(1-2):70-79.
12. Gipson, I. K. Distribution of mucins at the ocular surface. *Experimental eye research* 2004, 78 (3), 379-388.
13. Lee, J. W.; Park, J. H.; Robinson, J. R. Bioadhesive-based dosage forms: The next generation. *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences* 2000, 89 (7), 850-866.
14. Ludwig, A., 2005. The use of mucoadhesive polymers in ocular drug delivery. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 57, 1595-1639.
15. Agibayeva LE, Kaldybekov DB, Porfiryeva NN, Garipova VR, Mangazbayeva RA, Moustafine RI, Semina II, Mun GA, Kudaibergenov SE, Khutoryanskiy VV. Gellan gum and its methacrylated derivatives as in situ gelling mucoadhesive formulations of pilocarpine: In vitro and in vivo studies. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics.* 2020; 577:119093.
16. Tatykhanova G, Aseyev V, Vamvakaki M, Khutoryanskiy V, Kudaibergenov S. Ophthalmic drug delivery system based on the complex of gellan and ofloxacin. *Chem Bull Kaz Nat Univ.* 2022; 2:4-12.
17. Bajaj IB, Survase SA, Saudagar PS, Singhal, RS, Gellan gum: Fermentative production, downstream processing and applications. *Food Technol. Biotechnol.* 2007; 45:341-354.
18. Giavasis I, Harvey LM, Neil McB. Gellan gum. *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology.* 2000; 20:177-211.
19. Morris ER, Katsuyoshi N, Rinaudo M. Gelation of gellan. A review. *Food Hydrocolloids.* 2012; 28(2):373-414.
20. Hacker MC, Nawaz HA. Multi-functional macromers for hydrogel design in biomedical and regenerative medicine. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences.* 2015; 16(11):27677-27706.
21. Lavikainen J, Dauletbekova M, Toletay G, Kaliva M, Chatzinikolaidou M, Kudaibergenov SE, Tenkovtsev A, Khutoryanskiy VV, Vamvakaki M, Aseyev V. Poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline) grafted gellan gum for potential application in transmucosal drug delivery. *Polymers for Advanced Technologies.* 2021; 32(7):2770-2780.

22. Singh SR, Carreiro ST, Chu J, Niesman MR, Collette WW, Younis HS, Sartnurak S, Gukasyan HJ. L-Carnosine: multifunctional dipeptide buffer for sustained-duration topical ophthalmic formulations. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2009; 61(6):733-742.
23. Khutoryanskiy VV. Advances in mucoadhesion and mucoadhesive polymers. *Macromol. Biosci*. 2011; 11:748–764.
24. Irmukhametova GS; Mun GA; Khutoryanskiy VV. Thiolated mucoadhesive and PEGylated nonmucoadhesive organosilica nanoparticles from 3-mercaptopropyltrimethoxysilane. *Langmuir* 2011; 27:9551–9556.
25. Moiseev RV; Steele F; Khutoryanskiy VV. Polyaphron Formulations Stabilised with Different Water-Soluble Polymers for Ocular Drug Delivery. *Pharmaceutics* 2022; 14:926.
26. Lin HR; Sung KC. Carbopol/pluronic phase change solutions for ophthalmic drug delivery. *J. Control. Release* 2000; 69:379–388.
27. Van Haeringen NJ. Clinical biochemistry of tears. *Surv. Ophthalmol*. 1981; 26:84–96.
28. Fuoss RM. Viscosity function for polyelectrolytes. *J. Polym. Sci*. 1948; 3:603-604.
29. Fuoss RM. Errata: Viscosity function for polyelectrolytes. *J. Polym. Sci*. 3 (1948) 603-604. *J. Polym. Sci*. 1949; 4:96-96.
30. Dreveton E, Monot F, Lecourtier J, Ballerini D, Choplin L. Influence of fermentation hydrodynamics on gellan gum physic-chemical characteristics. *J. Fermentation and Bioeng*. 1996; 82(3):272-276.
31. Gong Y, Wang C, Lai RC, Su K, Zhang F, Wang D. An improved injectable polysaccharide hydrogel: modified gellan gum for long-term cartilage regeneration in vitro. *J. Mater. Chem*. 2009; 19(14):1968-1977.
32. Tatykhanova G, Aseyev V, Kudaibergenov S. Mucoadhesive Properties of Gellan and Its Modified Derivatives. *Reviews and Advances in Chemistry*. 2020; 10(2-3):140-157.
33. Al Khateb K, Ozhmukhametova EK, Mussin MN, Seilkanov SK, Rakhypbekov TK, Lau WM, Khutoryanskiy VV. In situ gelling systems based on Pluronic F127/Pluronic F68 formulations for ocular drug delivery. *Int. J. Pharm*. 2016; 502:70–79.
34. Tonglairoum P, Brannigan RP, Opanasopit P, Khutoryanskiy VV. Maleimide-bearing nanogels as novel mucoadhesive materials for drug delivery. *J. Mater. Chem. B*. 2016; 4:6581–6587.
35. Moiseev RV, Kaldybekov DB, Filippov SK, Radulescu A, Khutoryanskiy VV. Maleimide-Decorated PEGylated Mucoadhesive Liposomes for Ocular Drug Delivery. *Langmuir* 2022; 38:13870–13879.
36. Davidovich-Pinhas M, Bianco-Peled H. Methods to study mucoadhesive dosage forms. In *Mucoadhesive Materials and Drug Delivery Systems*. Khutoryanskiy VV Ed. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons Ltd. 2014. 175–196 pp. ISBN 9781118794203.
37. Destruel PL, Zeng N, Maury M, Mignet N, Boudy V. *In vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation of *in situ* gelling systems for sustained topical ophthalmic delivery: State of the art and beyond. *Drug Discovery Today*. 2017; 22 (4):638-651
38. Thrimawithana TR, Rupenthal ID, Young SA, Alany RG. Environment sensitive polymers for ophthalmic drug delivery. *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol*. 2012; 22:117–124.

ORCID ID of Authors

Gulnur S. Tatykhanova: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4457-1705>
 Rysgul N. Tuleyeva: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9691-4274>
 Nargiz N. Gizatullina <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4230-1031>
 Yuliia V. Bardadym <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9809-0897>
 Daulet B. Kaldybekov: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7191-5465>
 Vladimir O. Aseyev: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3739-8089>
 Sarkyt E. Kudaibergenov: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1166-7826>

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP13067773) and was supported by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program of the European Union Maria Skłodowska-Curie (grant agreement 823883-NanoPol-MSCA-RISE-2018).

ABBREVIATIONS

GG, Gellan gum; NaFI, fluorescein sodium salt; FITC-dextran, fluorescein isothiocyanate-labeled dextran; STF, simulated tear fluid.

Supplementary Materials

Characterization of Biocompatible Gellan Gum Fractions for Prolonged Retention in Ocular Drug Delivery Systems

Gulnur S. Tatykhanova^{1,2,*}, Rysgul N. Tuleyeva^{2,3}, Nargiz N. Gizatullina^{1,2}, Daulet B. Kaldybekov^{2,3}, Yuliia V. Bardadym⁴, Vladimir O. Aseyev⁴ and Sarkyt E. Kudaibergenov^{2*}

¹ *Laboratory of engineering profile, Satbayev University, 050013 Almaty, Kazakhstan*

² *Institute of Polymer Materials and Technology, 050019 Almaty, Kazakhstan*

³ *Department of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, 050040 Almaty, Kazakhstan*

⁴ *Department of Chemistry, University of Helsinki, 00560 Helsinki, Finland*

*Corresponding authors:

Gulnur S. Tatykhanova

Email: gulnur-ts81@yandex.kz

Sarkyt E. Kudaibergenov

Email: skudai@mail.ru

Figure S1. Dependence of the reduced viscosity of purified GG on polymer concentration in pure water.

Figure S2. The intrinsic viscosity of purified commercial GG determined by Fuoss equation.

Fractionation of GG by fractional dissolution

Figure S3. Stages of the GG purification: (1) turbid 1% "solution" of gellan in deionized water 24 hours after dissolution at 50 °C; (2) gellan in water after centrifugation for 30 minutes at 40 °C at a spin speed of 5000 rpm; (3) the pre-settling liquid after centrifugation, which is precipitated with acetone (1:4 by volume); (4) sediment separated from the water-acetone mixture by vacuum

filtration; (5) dry gellan after freeze-drying. Subsequent fractionation of the polymer is carried out with the precipitate isolated after stage 2.

Table S1. Yield of GG fractions obtained by fractional dissolution

Fractions	Pore size of dialysis membranes, kDa	Yield, %
GG-1	12-14	30.2
GG-2	12-14	18.8
GG-3	12-14	14.8
GG-4	12-14	9.6
Insoluble precipitate		19.8

Table S2. Yield of GG fractions obtained by ultrasonic treatment

Fractions	Ultrasonic treatment time, min	Pore size of dialysis membranes, kDa	Yield, %
1-GG	5	12-14	3.9
2-GG	10	12-14	2.4
3-GG	30	6-8	39.9
4-GG	60	3.5	24.1
5-GG	120	3.5	42.8

An elemental analysis was conducted on both the initial and purified GG. The nitrogen content in both GG samples was found to be very low, as detailed in Table S3, indicating that proteins were not present.

Table S3. Elemental analysis of GG samples

Biopolymer	Element content (w-%)			
	Nitrogen	Carbon	Hydrogen	Sulfur
Commercial GG	0.05	36.31	5.60	0.00
Purified GG	0.06	38.59	5.89	0.00